

An Analysis of the Informational Content of Dividend Change Payments at Amman Stock Exchange

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Abstract

This study investigates the market reaction to dividend change announcements for the period 1996 to 2002 at Amman Stock Exchange. Event study methodology is applied to examine the significance of mean abnormal return on and around the announcement date, the trading model of Scholes and Williams is applied and parametric and non parametric tests are used. Also, this study applies ZD test that corrects for the misspecifications related to the market model. The results show that the market reacts negatively to dividend change announcements and no pre-event information leakage for the samples studied. The conclusion doesn't appear to support signalling hypothesis and suggests dividends in Jordan are a residual payment that is consistent with Mollah (2001).

Keywords: Dividend Payments, Signalling Hypothesis, Event Study Methodology

1. Introduction

Financial markets play a crucial role in facilitating the intermediation between savers and investors, thereby helping translate savings into investments. The more efficient this process is, the less the cost

of investing, and subsequently, the higher the rate of investment and saving. The development of stock exchanges is crucial to achieve economic growth for developing economies. The increasing globalisation of financial markets has heightened interest in emerging markets. However, much of the research in accounting and finance has focused on developed markets, in particular, the US and European markets. The assumptions that underpin the models employed in developed markets provide a challenge when examining emerging markets such as Jordan. In an uncertain economic environment, characterized by informational asymmetry, the announcement of changes in corporate finance variables (e.g., dividends) are often regarded as signals emitted by company management which have to be interpreted by outside investors in developed countries. Since the documented evidence suggests that these announcements convey private information to the market, numerous signalling models have been developed to explain the accompanying share price reaction to such announcements.

Since its establishment in 1978, Amman Stock Exchange has experienced a remarkable development and it has become one of the most active and organized markets among the emerging markets. It plays an important role in financing development in Jordan. Jordan's capital market was increasingly viewed as a critical component in the economic development plans of the country. The Jordanian government adopted a comprehensive capital market reforming policy, which aimed at building on the previous 20 years' experience, boosting the private sector, expanding and diversifying the national economy, and improving regulation of the securities market to international standards. Among the most important features of the new orientation were institutional changes in the capital market, use of international electronic trading, settlement and clearance systems, elimination of obstacles to investment, and strengthening capital market supervision to reach optimum transparency and safe trading in securities. Although many studies have been conducted on dividend signalling and information content of dividend in developed markets, there is no such comprehensive study found about the effectiveness of the dividend announcement as a signalling device to influence the security prices of an emerging market. Therefore, the existing published evidence is of limited relevance in investigating the market reaction to dividend announcement and in identifying the appropriate dividend policy and behaviour in the emerging market, and still these issues of market reaction to dividend announcement and dividend policy and behaviour of an emerging market remain unresolved.

This study will contribute to the literature by providing empirical evidence of the market's reaction to dividend announcements in Jordan. Information content studies provide the opportunity to understand the markets' assessment of dividend payments, and consequently, to help for a better understanding of the dividend policies of Jordanian firms. This is important for investors, regulators, and management. The objective of this study is to investigate the market reaction to dividend change announcements on the Amman Stock Exchange. Specifically, how the market reacts when the change in dividend payment from the previous year is positive, negative, and unchanged. This objective will be achieved by reviewing the literature of the signalling hypothesis in Jordan, applying the event study methodology to measure the market's reaction to the change in dividend payments on the announcement date.

The remainder of this study is organised as follows. Section 2 presents literature review. Research methodology is described in section 3, while section 4 and 5 present hypotheses development and sample selection, respectively. Section 6 discusses the empirical results and section 7 provides the conclusion.

2. Literature Review: The Signalling Model

The assumptions of Modigliani and Millers' theory (1959) stated that the current value of the firm is independent of the method of financing, and the firm's main objective is to maximise shareholders value. Thus, the market value of a firm is not affected by its dividend policy. They assumed perfect capital markets, rational investors' behaviour and no tax discrimination between sources of income.

Miller and Modigliani (1961) argued that in a world without any market imperfections like taxes, transactions costs or asymmetric information, a firm's dividend policy should have no effect on

its market value. An important assumption to this argument is the independence of firm's investment policy from its dividend policy. Hence, the irrelevance argument holds only if investment decisions are not influenced by management's insistence on maintaining or raising the firm's dividend.

Accordingly, the market imperfection of asymmetric information is the basis to explain corporate dividend policy. The mitigation of the information asymmetries between managers and owners via unexpected changes in dividend policy is the cornerstone of dividend-signalling models. Ross (1977), Bhattacharya (1979), Hakansson (1982), John and Williams (1985), Miller and Rock (1985), Ambarish, John and Williams (1987), Bar-Yosef and Huffman (1988), and many others offer signalling models of corporate dividend policy. The proponents of signalling theories believe that corporate dividend policy can be used as a means of putting the message of quality. Dividends have a lower cost than other alternatives. The use of dividends as signals implies that alternative methods of signalling are not perfect substitutes.

One of the important implications of this signalling argument is that it suggests the possibility of optimal dividend policy. The signalling benefits from paying dividends may be traded off against the tax disadvantages in order to achieve an optimal payout. Bhattacharya (1979) suggested that, if stockholders have imperfect information about firms' profitability, and if there is a tax rate differential between capital gains and dividends, then dividends will be a surrogate for a signal of expected cash flows. John and Williams (1985) developed Bhattacharya's signalling model in the context of a tax penalty on dividends over capital gains. Corporate insiders with more valuable private information optimally distribute larger dividends and receive higher prices for their stock whenever the demand for cash by both their firm and its current stockholders exceeds its internal supply of cash.

Ofer and Thakor (1987), Ambarish, John and Williams (1987), Bar-Yosef and Huffman (1988), John and Lang (1991), Hausch and Seward (1993) and Noe and Rebello (1996) present further analysis of dividend signalling models. These models extend earlier approaches by focusing on firms that signal simultaneously with dividends, investment or, equivalently, dividends and stock repurchase. These multiple signal models recognise that the change in the firm's dividend policy cannot be evaluated independently of other management decisions or firm characteristics. Although these signalling models provide important insights into why firms signal via dividends, and consequently why the market reaction to an increase in dividends is positive and to dividend decrease is negative, they rely on restrictive assumptions (for example, John and Williams model assumes all equity financing and homogeneous expectations by investors). However, these models do not resolve the central issue of what information management signal (or hope to signal) to the market via dividend announcements. So, the question is why the dividend increase is always treated by the market as good news and the dividend decrease as a bad news.

One of the primary literatures that investigated the stock price reaction to dividend announcements was conducted by Pettit (1972). Therefore, number of empirical studies followed the theoretical work of signalling models mentioned by Bhattacharya (1979), John and Williams (1985) and Miller and Rock (1985) and the primary work of Pettit (1972), and it has been the source of debate on the information content of dividend (e.g., Charest (1978), Aharony and Swary (1980), Asqith and Mullins (1983), Eades, Hess and Kim (1985), Michaely, Thaler and Womack (1995), Impson (1997), McCaffrey and Hamill (2000), Fukuda (2000), Mollah (2001), and Travlos, Trigeorgis, and Vafeas (2001)). These debates based on the idea that insiders of a firm have better information regarding the firm's earnings potential than do market participants, and that to maximize share holder wealth, insiders reveal this information to the market by taking some observable action. The market subsequently uses this new information to update its expectations regarding the firm's earnings prospects, and as a result of this process a new stock price is determined. The existence of asymmetric information in the market makes dividends "relevant", and changes in dividends are therefore a source of information about a firm's earnings potential.

Two studies examine the effect of dividend changes announcements on emerging markets. Mollah (2001) investigated whether dividend announcements conveyed information to the market or whether investors considered the announcement of dividends as a signal of firms' future prospects in

Bangladesh. He applied the event study methodology for 153 firms over 1988-1997, and his final sample was consisting of 380 cash dividend announcements amongst 213 dividend increasing announcements, 84 dividend decreasing announcements, and 83 dividend maintaining announcements. He did not find a significant impact of dividend announcement on the security prices and further no evidence to support the dividend-signalling hypothesis. Furthermore, he found a similarity among his samples when he found that security prices is decreasing after increasing dividends, decreasing dividends, and maintaining dividends, which he indicated it as an ineffectiveness of the announcements of dividends in Bangladesh. He mentioned that insiders are holding higher proportion of stocks, so, usually insiders start to buy back the shares before the general assembly meeting for higher voting rights, moreover, insiders off load shares after the general assembly meeting start to sell their shares and that causes higher supply of shares and consequently returns fall. Moreover, Mollah (2001) studied the determination of dividend policy in Bangladesh. He found that leverage, size, insider ownership, and collateralizable assets are the major determinants of dividend payout ratio in Bangladesh. While supporting the agency cost hypothesis and the transaction cost hypothesis, his analysis of the determination of dividend policy did not support the signalling hypothesis, the tax clientele hypothesis, the residual hypothesis, and the pecking order hypothesis.

3. Research Methodology

One of the quantitative methods that have been used widely in conducting the dividend change effect is event methodology and it is one of the most frequently used statistical techniques in the applied financial research. Initial event studies emerged in the United States three decades ago (Ball and Brown, 1968; Beaver, 1968; Fama, Fisher, Jensen, and Roll 1969; and Kaplan and Roll, 1972), and have continually been extended (Brown and Warner, 1980, 1985; Blume and Stambaugh, 1983; Dyckman et al, 1984; Morse, 1984; Schipper and Smith, 1986; and Fama and French, 1992). Event studies are used to measure the impact of an economic event on firm value. Assuming that the event will be reflected in traded asset prices, these studies focus on how asset prices respond to information releases during a public announcement of the event.

The objective of an event study is to measure whether there are any abnormal or excess returns earned by security holders accompanying special events (e.g., dividend announcements). The results of event studies not only can have serious implications in forming accounting or government policy, but also provide an important source of market information to both individual and institutional investors (Beaver, 1988). On the other hand, event studies can also be used to study market efficiency on the semi-strong form by analysing the market reactions to these 'events' (Firth, 1979). The event study methodology has become popular because it obviates the need to analyze accounting-based measures of profit, which have been criticized because they are often not very good indicators of the true performance of firms. For example, managers can manipulate accounting profits because they can select accounting procedures (Benston, 1982). Stock prices on the other hand, are not as subject to manipulation by insiders. Stock prices are supposed to reflect the true value of firms, because they are assumed to reflect the discounted value of all future cash flows and incorporate all relevant information. Therefore, event studies, which are based on stock price changes, should measure the financial impact of a change in corporate policy, leadership, or ownership more effectively than a methodology based on accounting returns. Furthermore, the event study method is relatively easy to implement, because the only data necessary are the names of publicly traded firms, event dates, and stock prices. The major elements in conducting event study methodology is, specifying the event date, specifying the estimation and event period, and calculating the daily returns. To achieve the research question, we will adapt the event study methodology for the above reasons and for the following: (1) this method calculates abnormal return by differentiating the actual returns and expected returns calculate based on previous performance (2) Abnormal returns are the best reflection for the announcements (3) As the Amman stock exchange is an emerging market, it is important to conduct event study on a longer period, which this method helps to do. This study explains the Event Study

Methodology that includes specifying the event date, the estimation period, the event period, and the equations and test statistics that will be applied.

3.1. Specifying of Event Date, Estimation period, and Event period

The event date is often recognised as the release date of new information to market participants through the financial press or through corporate release. The identification of event date is of prime important because the correct event date can provide a powerful test of the information content of announcements. To investigate the market reaction to dividend change announcements on Amman Stock Exchange, we will use the general assembly meeting date to consider the event date. According to the Jordanian company law 1997, article 190 A and B, which reveals that the right entitling shareholder to obtain their shares of the company's profits accrues on the date of adopting a resolution by the general assembly regarding distribution of dividends and the right to receive the profit against the company for the shareholders shall be on the date of the meeting of the general assembly on which it decides to distribute its profits. According to this, we see that the most important date in which the dividends are officially approved and the public knows about the dividend decisions are notified on this day. Furthermore, on the general assembly meeting, the shares are not allowed to be traded on the market according to the listing securities regulation on Amman Stock Exchange (Article 26-a of the Securities Law no. 23 of 1997). So, the following day of the GAM day is the announcement day.

The estimation period is used for estimating the parameters of the benchmark expected return. This allows predicted abnormal returns to be calculated within the test period. Most of event studies establish the estimation period prior to the event period. This is mainly based on an assumption that the normal or predicted returns over the estimation period will be independent with the release of the events if there is no leakage of the information before the announcements.

Brown and Warner (1980, 1985) and Peterson (1989) mentioned that daily returns are more powerful than monthly returns. Morse (1984) supported the use of daily return data to estimate information effects, with the possible exception of cases in which there is uncertainty about the date of the information release. Morse (1984) mentioned that even with this uncertainty, however, daily returns may still be preferred to monthly returns. His analytical results were consistent with some empirical results in Brown and Warner (1980, 1983) and Dyckman, Philbrick, and Stephan (1982). Because most of the previous researches employed daily data and to allow comparing the results with the previous ones, this study will employ the daily rather than the monthly data. This study will use 130 trading daily observations as the estimation period from day $T=-21$ to Time $1=-150$ before the event period.

Selection of the length of the event period is also subjective. Typical lengths of the event period range from 21 to 121 days for daily studies and from 25 months to 121 months for monthly studies (Peterson, 1989). However, the calculated abnormal returns over a narrow event period around announcements might understate the usefulness of information, if the period fails to capture information-induced price revisions beyond the period. On the other hand, abnormal returns calculated by using wide event period, might overstate the information contribution of announcements, as price changes within the period probably reflect investors' reaction to other timely information published (Lev, 1989). This study will use 41 trading days, covering the period $T+1=-20$ to $T+m=+20$.

3.2. Calculating Daily Returns and Return Generating Models

The return is computed as the natural logarithms of the stock price relatives given by the equation below.

$$R_{i,t} = \log_e(P_{i,t} + D_{i,t}) - \log_e P_{i,t-1} \quad (1)$$

Where, $R_{i,t}$ is the daily stock returns for security i at day t , $\log_e P_{i,t-1}$ is the natural logarithm of the stock price i at day $t-1$, $\log_e P_{i,t}$ is the natural logarithm of the stock price i at day t , and $D_{i,t}$ is The dividend on security i at day t . The returns on Amman Stock Exchange index are computed as the natural logarithm of the first differences of the market index according to the equation below.

$$R_t = \log_e I_t - \log_e I_{t-1} \quad (2)$$

Where, R_t is the market return at day t, $\log_e I_{t-1}$ is the natural logarithm price index of the market at the end of day t-1, and $\log_e I_t$ is the natural logarithm of price index of the market at the end of day t. Abnormal return analysis, which is at the core of information content studies, requires an appropriate return generating benchmark. In the literature, there are several return-generating models. The use of a particular return model depends on the nature of data at hand and on the specification of the model itself. The following are the most frequently used return generating models in the literature The Market Model, The Mean-Adjusted Return Model and The market-Adjusted Model.

As a consequence of non-synchronise trading, OLS estimates of the market model parameters will be biased and inconsistent resulting in biased estimates of abnormal returns and consequently mis-specified test statistics in event studies. To take the account of this problem, Scholes and Williams (1977), Dimson (1979), Flower and Rorke (1983) and Cohen et al (1983), provided methods to remove a greater deal of bias from beta. The Scholes-Williams and the Fowler-Rorke methods are the only two thin trading adjustment methods that will be employed in this study.

3.3. Abnormal Return (AR) and Cumulative Abnormal Return (CAR)

The abnormal return is the difference between the firm's actual and estimated returns. Any significant abnormal returns in the test period may be attributed to the information content of dividend change announcement. These abnormal returns are used to investigate whether the event being considered has resulted in significant excess return. Mathematically, abnormal returns were calculated as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{i,t} = R_{i,t} - \hat{R}_{i,t} \quad (3)$$

Where, $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is the excess (abnormal) return of firm i at day t, $R_{i,t}$ is the actual (raw) return of firm i at day t, and $\hat{R}_{i,t}$ is the estimated return of firms i at day t applying the robust market mode, Scholes and Williams adjusted market model, and the Mean adjusted model. The abnormal returns will average across individual observations as follows:

$$MAR_t = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4)$$

Where, MAR_t is the mean abnormal return at day t, N is the number of observations, and $\varepsilon_{i,t}$ is the abnormal return of firm i at day t. The mean abnormal return used to investigate if there is any excess return on individual days, and this will enable us to measure the market reaction to dividend changes announcements when they have been released to the market. The cumulative abnormal return (CAR) is a sum of an individual period abnormal return over a number of periods. The cumulative abnormal returns over holding periods, from day m1 to day m2, are calculated as follows:

$$CAR_{m_1, m_2} = \sum_{t=m_1}^{m_2} MAR_t \quad (5)$$

As noted by Brown and Warner (1985) and Strong (1992), where there is uncertainty regarding the event day and even if the event date is known with certainty, it is not always clear when the information content of the event becomes available. So, cumulative abnormal return comes to resolve this problem by taking a sum of individual abnormal returns.

3.4. Parametric and Non-parametric Tests

The parametric tests proposed in the literature rely on the important assumption that individual firm's abnormal returns are normally distributed. We will employ two parametric tests in this study namely, the t-test, and Coutt's ZD test. Hamill, Opong and McGregor (2002) provide details of the ZD test which accounts fully for the increased variance of prediction errors outside of the estimation period and for the cumulating of these errors across different event windows. It also takes account of the fact that

market model residuals are typically serially correlated, heteroscedastic and non-normal. The ZD-test will be used in this study to investigate the price performance in different event windows around the announcements of dividend changes.

Also, this study will employ Corrado's non-parametric rank test. Under the assumption of no cross-sectional correlation, the statistic is distributed unit normal. Cowen and Sergeant (1996) showed that if the return variance is unlikely to increase, then Corrado's rank test provides better specification and power than parametric tests. Seiler (2000) justify using Corrado's test is that Corrado (1989) developed a nonparametric rank test which is correctly specified independent of the degree of skewness in the cross-sectional distribution of abnormal returns. Further, this nonparametric rank test is found to be less affected by event-induced variance. Maynes and Rumsey (1993) pointed that Corrado's test shows that the test statistic derived from the ranks is superior for testing for presence of abnormal return and the success of that test arises because the distribution of ranks is uniform.

4. Sample Selection

This study expands over seven years from 1996-2002 covering all the industrial firms. This leads to identify 360 observations distributed on the whole sample period from 1996-2002. Our sample selection process consists of two stages; in the first stage 56 observations will be excluded from the whole sample. The observation will be excluded if, as outlined earlier, dividends and earnings are announced simultaneously. Hence the announcement date refers to the date at which the firms announce their dividend and earnings change. However, in order to mitigate the effect of other contemporaneous events, it is necessary to eliminate any contemporaneous events surrounding the dividend and earning announcement date, such as stock dividend and split, or mergers and acquisitions that may contaminate the stock price movement. Consistent with Howe and Shen (1998) and Kosedag and Micayluk (2000), any observation with an announcement other than dividend and earnings announcement, made on the 41 days test period from -20 to 20 around the event date, will be eliminated from the study. This resulted in (26) observations being eliminated. An observation will be also excluded if the announcement date is not available and cannot be determined for some observations, if this is the case, any observation without an event date will be eliminated. This resulted to eliminate (21) observations from the sample. And finally, An observation will be also excluded if it is suspended or reintroduced, because of reporting problems or financial losses will be eliminated from the study, these firms are unlikely to have a consistent run of daily stock price data in order to generate returns and hence will be eliminate from the sample. This resulted in (9) observation to be eliminated.

In the second stage some information content studies set a criterion to select only firms with high trading activities like Rippinton and Taffler (1995). Following Al-Ghamidi (1998), observations should have had at least 60% trading days. The justification is that non-trading days result in zero returns, which in turn bias the results. This resulted to eliminate 107 observations from the sample.

As our aim is to investigate the market reaction to the change on dividends and if they reflect information content when they have been released. Four groups have been mentioned on developing the hypothesis depending on the dividend per share for each observation for time t comparing it with the previous dividend per share $t-1$. Each group will represent a sample for the purpose of this study, as follows:

If $DPS_t > DPS_{t-1}$: then any observation meet this equation will consider as dividend increase.

If $DPS_t < DPS_{t-1}$: then any observation meet this equation will consider as dividend decrease.

If $DPS_t = DPS_{t-1}$: then any observation meet this equation will consider as dividend no change.

Furthermore, dividend no change could be with dividends and without dividends. According to that, this sample will be divided to two sub-samples; the first dividend no change sample, and the second no dividend no change sample.

The final sample is 197 observations. After investigating the changes in dividend and applying the above methodology, we observed 38 observations of those relating to the dividend increase, 34 of

those to the dividend decrease, 24 observations related to dividend no change, and 101 observations related to no change no dividend (see Table 1 and Table 2 below).

Table 1: Number of Observations Eliminated at Each Stage of the Selection Process

Period	No. of observations	Stage1	Stage2	Total
1996	41	2	16	23
1997	46	3	20	23
1998	48	11	13	24
1999	50	11	17	22
2000	46	11	15	20
2001	64	10	10	44
2002	65	8	16	41
Total	360	56	107	197

Table 2: Number of Observations for Each Sample

Dividend Samples	Observations
Dividend Increase Sample	38
Dividend Decrease Sample	34
Dividend No Change Sample	24
No Dividend No Change Sample	101
Total	197

Daily stock prices information over the period 1996 till 2002 were collected from Jordan Security Commission (JSC), Amman Stock Exchange (ASE), and Security Depository Centre (SDE). Daily stock prices and value-weighted price indexes were collected for the industrial firms all over the period of study, and then it was computerised. From the same source, dividends and their ex-dates over the period of study were collected. Other information like stock split, stock dividend, merger, acquisition, capital increase and decrease were collected for the purpose of not including the observations that announce any of these events around the announcement date. Other sources like company reports and the stock market publications like monthly statistical bulletin and annual report, company's guide, and the daily official list were used to check the information collected for accuracy.

The justification of using the naïve model in this study is that, no available information in Amman stock exchange about the dividend forecasts from the market or from the analysts to compare the actual dividend with these expectations. Also, to compare our results with that obtained by Mollah (2001) who used the naïve model in his study. Previous literature like Aharony and Swary (1980), Eddy and Seifert (1992), and Opong (1997) applied the naïve model in their study.

6. Empirical Results: Mean Abnormal Return and Cumulative Abnormal Return

6.1. Descriptive Statistics

Table 3 reports the distribution of proprieties of dividends on ASE. It reports summary statistics for the whole sample selected for the period 1996 to 2002.

Table 3: Summary Statistics for the Dividends Sample from 1996 to 2002

Dividend Type ¹	1996	1997	1998	1999	2000	2001	2002	Row Total	% Total
DI	4	3	3	1	6	14	7	38	19.3
DD	4	5	7	5	4	1	6	34	17.3
DNC	1	3	1	3	2	8	6	24	12.2
NDNC	12	12	13	13	8	21	22	101	51.2
Total	23	23	24	22	20	44	41	197	100
Total%	11.7	11.7	12.2	11.2	10.2	22.3	20.7	100	-

Note: ¹ DI= Dividend Increase, DD= Dividend Decrease, DNC= Dividend no Change, NDND= No Dividend no change in Dividend.

Table 3 shows that year 2001 and 2002 achieved 43 percent of the entire sample while years 1996 to 2000 were 57 percent. This means that the most of our sample was collected from two years; 2001 and 2002. The construction of the sample required that the trading days for each observation to be more than 60% of its daily trading and then most of the observations achieved this requirement occurred on the years 2001 and 2002 comparing with the previous years. Also, table 6.1 make clear that the no dividend no change sample observed the highest percentage of observations between the entire samples.

Table 4 reports the proprieties of the market value and it reports summary statistics for the four samples: the mean, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, minimum, median, maximum, normality test, and number of observations.

Table 4: The Dividend Change Samples for the Period 1996-2002

Descriptive	M.Value DI	M.Value DD	M.Value DNC	M.Value NDNC	M.Value ALL
Mean ¹	37	48,4	53,9	18,6	31,6
StDev ¹	67,1	111	94,9	50,3	74
Skewness	2.8	3.1	3.6	4.6	3.9
Kurtosis	7.7	10.2	14.7	24.6	18
Minimum ¹	1,5	1,7	2	0,4	0,4
Median ¹	11	7,7	17,5	4,7	6,6
Maximum ¹	306	517	454	359	517
Normality ²	7.2	7.9	3.6	25.3	41.9
N. Obs	38	34	24	101	197

Note: ¹ Numbers in millions Jordan Dinnar.

² A-Squared Anderson-Darling Normality Test

Table 4 shows that the highest mean market value was for the dividend no change sample. It is clear from this table that the lowest mean market value was observed for the no dividend no change sample and it observed the lowest mean market value comparing with those samples which have dividends. The skewness statistics, which assess the symmetry of the distribution, is positive, which indicate generally a highly skewed distribution. The kurtosis coefficient is greater than zero, which indicates that the distribution inhabit some large observations. The kurtosis coefficient measures the relative peakness or flatness of the distribution, compared with the normal distribution. The kurtosis coefficient is positive which indicates that the data is peaked. A negative kurtosis value would indicate a relatively flat distribution.

The Anderson-Darling normality test was also performed. The null hypothesis for this test is that the market value for the sample of dividends is normally distributed. The results demonstrate that the market value for the selected sample exhibited a high degree of non-normality which means that we accept the null hypothesis of the normality test.

Table 5 shows the actual average dividend per share for each sample in our study. It is clear that the highest average dividend per share was observed for the dividend no change sample with 18%, then for the dividend increase sample with 16.8%, and then for the dividend decrease sample with 9%.

Table 5: The Average Dividend per Share (DPS) for Each Sample in the Study

Sample Type	Number of observations	Actual Average DPS
Dividend Increase Sample	38	9%
Dividend Decrease Sample	34	16.9%
Dividend No Change Sample	24	18%
No Dividend No Change Sample	101	0

6.2. Market Reaction to Dividend Announcements

Numerous studies for developed markets reported that changes in dividends and earnings conveys specific information to the market (e.g., Aharony and Swary (1980), Asqith and Mullins (1983), Woolridge (1983), Fehrs et al (1988), Woolridge and Ghosh (1988), Eddy and Seifert (1922), Michaely, Thaler and Womack (1995), Abeyratna et al (1997), Impson (1997), Travlos, Trigeorgis, and Vafeas (2001)). In general positive (negative) dividend change announcements produce positive (negative) security prices reaction. The few studies of emerging markets provide alternative results. Mollah (2001) concluded that the market reacts negatively for both dividend positive and negative announcements, clarifying that a decrease on the security share prices occurred for dividend increase and decrease samples. A summary of the major empirical studies on the security price reaction to the announcement of dividends along with the data set they used, research methodology, and their findings are presented in the table 6.

Table 6: Summary of the Expected Mean Abnormal Return and Cumulative Abnormal Return

Dividend Change	Expected $MAR_{(\tau=0)}$	Expected $CAR_{m1,m2} = 0$	
		Per-event	Post-event
Dividend Increase	Positive: $MAR > 0$	No Change: $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	Positive: $CAR_{0,20} = 0$
Dividend Decrease	Negative: $MAR < 0$	No Change: $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	Negative: $CAR_{0,20} = 0$
Dividend No change	No change: $MAR = 0$	No Change: $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	No Change: $CAR_{0,20} = 0$
No Dividend No change	No change: $MAR = 0$	No Change: $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	No Change: $CAR_{0,20} = 0$

After reviewing the previous empirical studies and their findings on table 7 summarises our expectations for the mean abnormal return and the cumulative abnormal return for the dividend increase, dividend decrease, dividend no change, and no dividend no change samples. A positive market reaction is expected to occur when dividend payments are increased comparing with the previous period, and accordingly, a positive mean abnormal return (MAR) is expected on the dividend announcement day (day 0). The expectation for the cumulative abnormal return on the pre-event period is zero, which would indicate that no information regarding dividends have been released before the announcement day. Therefore, if a positive market reaction occurred before the announcement day, this will be an indication to information leakage. On the other hand, a negative market reaction is expected when dividend payments are decreased compared with the previous period, and accordingly, a negative mean abnormal return will be observed on the dividend announcement day (day 0). The expectations for the cumulative abnormal return on the pre-event period is zero, which indicate that no information regarding dividends have been released before the announcement day. Therefore, if a negative market reaction occurred before the announcement day, this will be also an indication to information leakage. For both dividend no change sample and no dividend no change sample, no market reaction is expected to occur when dividend payments are not changing comparing with the previous period, and accordingly, no abnormal return will be observed on the dividend announcement day (day 0). Furthermore, the cumulative abnormal return on the post-event period is expected to be zero. The expectations for the cumulative abnormal return on the pre-event period are to be also zero, which means that no new information regarding dividends have been released to the market on the

announcement day. Therefore, if a positive or negative market reaction occurred before the announcement day for both dividend no change and no dividend no change samples, this will be an indication of misleading information or rumors.

Table 7: Mean Abnormal Return for 10 Days around the Dividend Announcements Applying the Market Adjusted with Scholes and Williams

Days	Dividend Increase Sample N=38		Dividend Decrease Sample N=34		Dividend No Change Sample N=24		No Dividend No Change Sample N=101	
	MAR %	AR<0%	MAR %	AR<0%	MAR %	AR<0%	MAR %	AR<0%
-5	-0.33	57.89	0.08	50.00	0.19	45.83	0.11	52.48
-4	0.23#	36.84	0.19	35.29	-0.01	45.83	0.20	50.50
-3	0.18	47.37	-0.42	58.82	-0.08	37.50	-0.15	48.51
-2	-0.16	55.26	0.42*#	35.29	-0.09	45.83	0.09	51.49
-1	0.03	44.74	-0.10	50.00	-0.85**	58.33	-0.04	43.56
0	-1.32*##	63.16	-1.50*##	64.71	-2.33*##	70.83	-0.66*##	54.46
1	-2.13*##	68.42	-0.99*##	76.47	-1.02**	50.00	-0.59*##	53.47
2	-0.62**	55.26	0.04	50.00	-0.91**	62.50	-0.28	53.47
3	0.01	36.84	-0.58*	55.88	-0.25	58.33	-0.01	49.51
4	-0.34	52.63	-0.08	50.00	0.11	54.17	0.28	46.53
5	0.05	52.63	0.06	50.00	-0.26	54.17	-0.18	48.51

Note: The results are consistent applying the market model, the mean adjusted model, the market adjusted model, the robust market model, and the market model adjusted with Flower and Rorke.

* Significant at the 5 percent level,

** Significant at the 1 percent level.

Significant at the 5 percent level,

Significant at the 1 percent level, when applying Corrado's non-parametric test.

6.3. Discussion of the Event Study Results

A summary of the event study results have been reported on table 8 and table 9. Also, figure 1 and 2 illustrate graphically the results for dividend increase, dividend decrease, dividend no change, and no dividend no change samples. Table 8 shows the mean abnormal return for 10 days (± 5) around the dividend announcements applying the market model adjusted with Scholes and Williams. The mean abnormal return is -1.32, -1.50, -2.33, and -.066 for the dividend increase, dividend decrease, dividend no change, and no dividend no change samples, respectively. Furthermore, the mean abnormal return is significant negative on the announcement day (day 0) at 1 percent level applying Scholes and Williams parametric test, and significant at 1 percent level applying the non-parametric Corrado's test except for the no dividend no change sample which is significant at 5 percent level. Moreover, the results did not change when other models were applied to generate the parameters. The market model, the mean adjusted model, the market adjusted model, the robust market model, and the market model adjusted with Flower and Rorke results were consistent with those results observed by applying Scholes and Williams model appeared on table 8. The parametric test shows that the market reaction was significant for both days 0 and 1, and for dividend increase and dividend no change samples, the market still reacts significantly on day 2. The empirical results show that security return decreases after the announcement of dividend increase, dividend decrease, dividend no change, and no dividend no change in Amman Stock Exchange. Even though, the empirical results of dividend decrease sample support the previous empirical studies, the empirical results of the dividend increase sample, dividend no change sample, and no dividend no change sample completely disagree with the previous empirical studies except for Mollah (2001). So, this is an indication of the ineffectiveness of the announcements of dividends in ASE. Our results are consistent with Mollah's results that a negative market reaction occurred when dividends are announced. Mollah (2001) concluded that: "... security prices is decreasing after the announcement of good news (increasing dividends), bad news (decreasing dividends), and no news (maintaining dividends). So, this is the indication of the ineffectiveness of the announcements of dividends in emerging markets."

Moreover, the consistent between our study and Mollahs' study comes from applying data from the emerging markets while applying data from Jordan, Mollah applied data from Bangladesh, and may be the characteristics underlying the emerging markets are different from their counterparts on the developed markets.

Table 8 summarises the cumulative abnormal return for 25 holding periods around the announcement day of dividends, and ZD test was used to report the results. This test correct the misspecifications which is related to the market model; non-normality, heteroscedasticity, and serially correlation. The cumulative abnormal returns were based on the market model adjusted with Scholes and Williams. The results show that the highest cumulative abnormal return was observed for the period from 0 to 2 days after the dividend announcements for the dividend increase, dividend decrease, and no dividend no change sample, and from 0 to 1 for the dividend decrease sample. Nevertheless, the most significant reaction occurred after the announcements and remains for 1 to 2 days after it. The pre-event period (-20, -1) did not observe a significant reaction for the four samples, which means that there is not information leakage before the announcements. The post-event period observed a significant negative market reaction except for the no dividend no change.

Table 9 Panel A and Panel B summaries the expected and actual mean and cumulative abnormal return for the dividend increase, dividend decrease, dividend no change, and no dividend no change samples. This table shows the result of investigate the market reaction to dividend announcements. On the mean abnormal return, the only sample which support our argument is the dividend decrease sample when it shows a negative market reaction realised after announcing dividend decreases, this is supported the previous studies on Table 6. Moreover, the cumulative abnormal return for the dividend decrease sample support our argument that after decreasing the dividends the security prices fall down, for the no dividend no change sample, no market reaction was observed for the post event period from 0 to 20 days after the announcement date. This conclusion supports the previous studies summarized on Table 6. The interpretation for the cumulative abnormal return of the no dividend no change sample that there is no change in security prices is that, the investors do not expect any dividend from those firms so they did not buy and hold these securities to get the right of getting cash dividend. Figure 1 and 2 support our finding and compare the four samples together. Even though, the dividend no change sample observed negative reaction than those dividend increases and dividend decreases, but the difference still insignificant. Furthermore, the figures show some differences when the market reacts to dividend announcements for the four samples, the dividend increase graph seems to be postponing the reaction until the first and second day after the announcements but in fact the reaction for the dividend increase sample begin on the announcement day (table 6.6 shows that the significant reaction begins on day 0). Moreover, the dividend no change sample is the one in which the market reaction of it begins before the announcement day, this is related to the sample size which is 24 observations, and then looking to the market reaction from the non-parametric point of view will give us the interpretation. Accordingly, the market reaction for the four samples is significant negative on the announcement day (day 0), which means that no differences graphically between the four samples.

Table 8: Summary of the Cumulative Abnormal Return for Selected Holding Periods on and around the Dividend Announcements

Holding Periods	Dividend Increase SampleN=38		Dividend Decrease SampleN=34		Dividend No Change SampleN=24		No Dividend No Change SampleN=101	
	CAR %	ZD-test	CAR %	ZD-test	CAR %	ZD-test	CAR%	ZD-test
(-20,-15)	-0.29	-0.51	0.14	0.21	0.26	0.36	-0.16	-0.29
(-20,-10)	0.07	0.09	0.72	0.78	0.61	0.63	0.31	0.41
(-20,-5)	0.31	0.32	0.91	0.80	0.09	0.08	0.53	0.58
(-20,-1)	0.24	0.22	1.18	0.92	0.10	0.08	0.80	0.76
(-20,5)	-4.14	-3.25**	-2.03	-1.37	-5.15	-3.32**	-0.51	-0.41
(-20,10)	-4.94	-3.47**	-2.91	-1.74	-6.21	-3.61**	-0.45	-0.32
(-20,15)	-4.57	-2.91**	-4.11	-2.23*	-6.80	-3.60**	-0.58	-0.38
(-20,20)	-4.92	-2.88**	-3.96	-1.99*	-6.10	-3.00**	0.49	0.30
(-2,0)	-1.45	-3.65**	-1.19	-2.55*	-3.28	-6.61**	-0.60	-1.61
(-2,1)	-3.58	-7.78**	-2.17	-4.02**	-4.30	-7.44**	-1.19	-2.74**
(-2,2)	-4.20	-8.15**	-2.13	-3.51**	-5.21	-8.02**	-1.48	-3.01**
(-2,3)	-4.19	-7.39**	-2.71	-4.05**	-5.46	-7.62**	-1.49	-2.76**
(-1,0)	-1.29	-4.00**	-1.61	-4.23**	-3.19	-7.92**	-0.70	-2.29*
(0,1)	-3.43	-8.63**	-2.59	-5.56**	-4.21	-8.47**	-1.29	-3.43**
(0,2)	-4.04	-8.81**	-2.55	-4.72**	-5.12	-8.88**	-1.57	-3.60**
(0,3)	-4.03	-7.82**	-3.13	-5.13**	-5.37	-8.27**	-1.59	-3.23**
(0,4)	-4.38	-7.72**	-3.21	-4.80**	-5.25	-7.42**	-1.30	-2.40*
(0,10)	-5.18	-6.56**	-4.09	-4.36**	-6.31	-6.49**	-1.25	-1.65
(0,15)	-4.81	-4.89**	-5.29	-4.55**	-6.90	-5.75**	-1.38	-1.48
(0,20)	-5.15	-4.46**	-5.14	-3.83**	-6.20	-4.48**	-0.31	-0.28
(3,20)	-1.73	-1.63	-2.55	-2.05*	-1.99	-1.57	0.98	0.99
(4,20)	-1.11	-1.08	-2.59	-2.16*	-1.08	-0.88	1.26	1.31
(5,20)	-1.12	-1.12	-2.01	-1.73	-0.83	-0.69	1.28	1.38
(10,20)	-0.35	-0.43	-1.33	-1.42	-0.35	-0.36	1.14	1.52
(15,20)	0.10	0.17	-0.04	-0.05	0.83	1.17	1.11	2.07*

Note: The cumulative abnormal return are based on the market model adjusted with Scholes and Williams, the test statistics for the ZD-test are distributed $N(0, 1)$.

* Significant at the 5 percent level,

** Significant at the 1 percent level.

Table 9: Summary of the Expected, Actual Mean Abnormal Return, Actual Cumulative Abnormal Return and the Hypotheses Findings

Panel A: Summary of the Expected and Actual Mean Abnormal Return and the Hypotheses Findings					
Dividend Change	Expected $MAR_{(\tau=0)}$		Actual $MAR_{(\tau=0)}$		Hypotheses Finding
Dividend Increase	Positive $MAR > 0$		Negative $MAR < 0$		There is no positive market reaction on and around the dividend payments for the dividend increase sample.
Dividend Decrease	Negative $MAR < 0$		Negative $MAR < 0$		There is a negative market reaction observed when dividend payments announced for the dividend decreases sample.
Dividend No change	No change $MAR = 0$		Negative $MAR < 0$		There is a negative market reaction following the dividend announcements for the dividend no changes sample.
No Dividend No change	No change $MAR = 0$		Negative $MAR < 0$		There is a negative market reaction following the dividend announcements for the no dividend no changes ample.
Panel B: Summary of the Expected and Actual Cumulative Abnormal Return and the Hypotheses Findings					
Dividend Change	Expected $CAR_{m1,m2} = 0$		Actual $CAR_{m1,m2} = 0$		Hypotheses Findings
	Per-event	Post-event	Pre-event	Post-event	
Dividend Increase	No Change $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	Positive $CAR_{0,20} = 0$	No Change $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	Negative $CAR_{0,20} < 0$	There is no significant positive cumulative abnormal return after the dividend payments announced for the dividend increases sample.
Dividend Decrease	No Change $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	Negative $CAR_{0,20} = 0$	No Change $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	Negative $CAR_{0,20} < 0$	There is a significant negative cumulative abnormal return after the dividend payments announced for the dividend decreases sample.
Dividend No Change	No Change $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	No Change $CAR_{0,20} = 0$	No Change $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	Negative $CAR_{0,20} < 0$	There is a significant negative change on the cumulative abnormal return after the dividend payments announced for the dividend no changes sample.
No Dividend No Change	No Change $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	No Change $CAR_{0,20} = 0$	No Change $CAR_{-20,-1} = 0$	No Change $CAR_{0,20} = 0$	There is not a significant change on the cumulative abnormal return for the no dividend no change sample.

Figure 1: Mean Abnormal for Dividend Announcements

Figure 2: Cumulative Abnormal Return for Dividend Announcements

7. Conclusion

The main objective of this study was to examine the market reaction to dividend change announcement (the information content of dividend). The signalling hypothesis suggests that good news is associated with a positive market reaction; while bad news is associated with a negative market reaction, and this phenomenon was supported by many studies (Aharony and Swary (1980), Opong (1995), amongst others). The previous literature supported the signalling hypothesis of dividends on developed markets like USA and Europe, few studies were found on Emerging markets. This study contributes to the literature by providing more evidence about market reaction of dividend announcements especially in Jordan.

The sample consisted of 197 observations spanned over the period 1996 to 2002. It was formulated into four groups namely dividend increase, dividend decrease, dividend no change, and no dividend no change. Event study methodology was applied to investigate the significance of the mean abnormal return on and around day 0 (general assembly meeting). The market model, market adjusted model, mean model were applied. Also, thin trading models were used that is market model adjusted with Scholes and Williams and market model adjusted with Flower and Rorke. Parametric and non parametric tests were used specifically, t-test, Corrado's rank test and ZD test which corrects for misspecifications related to the market model.

The results showed that the market reacted negatively to dividend increase and decrease samples, and the same result was obtained for the dividend no change sample. The conclusion of this result did not support the signalling model which is consistent with Mollah (2001). Also, the results showed no pre-event information leakage for any sample. This conclusion suggests that dividends in Jordan are a residual payment.

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